

THE INFLUENCE OF SOCIAL MEDIA ON DIGITAL LITERACY: A LINGUISTIC
ANALYSIS OF TELEGRAM COMMUNICATION**Mahkamova Matlubaxon Izzatillo qizi**

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15492045>

Abstract. *In today's digital age, literacy includes not only the ability to read and write but also to understand, interpret, and re-express information correctly. The development of technology and the widespread use of social media have negatively affected literacy levels. This study examines the decline in literacy due to syntactic and punctuation changes observed in Telegram and Instagram posts, highlighting the simplification and in formalization of written communication.*

Keywords: *digital literacy, social media communication, syntax and punctuation, Telegram, informal language, spelling errors, language change.*

Annotatsiya. *Bugungi raqamli asrda savodxonlik faqatgina o'qish va yozish qobiliyatini emas, balki ma'lumotni to'g'ri tushunish, talqin qilish va qayta ifodalash ko'nikmalarini ham o'z ichiga oladi. Texnologiyaning rivojlanishi va ijtimoiy tarmoqlarning keng tarqalishi savodxonlik darajasining pasayishiga salbiy ta'sir ko'rsatmoqda. Ushbu tadqiqot Telegram va Instagramdagi postlarda kuzatilayotgan sintaktik va punktuatsion o'zgarishlar orqali savodxonlikning pasayishini o'rganadi hamda yozma muloqotda soddalashuv va norasmiylashuv jarayonlarini yoritadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *raqamli savodxonlik, ijtimoiy tarmoqdagi muloqot, sintaksis va punktuatsiya, Telegram, norasmiy til, imlo xatolari, til o'zgarishi.*

Аннотация. *В современную цифровую эпоху грамотность включает не только умение читать и писать, но и способность правильно понимать, интерпретировать и переосмысливать информацию. Развитие технологий и широкое распространение социальных сетей оказывают негативное влияние на уровень грамотности. В данном исследовании рассматривается снижение уровня грамотности через синтаксические и пунктуационные изменения, наблюдаемые в постах на Telegram и Instagram, с акцентом на упрощение и неформализацию письменной коммуникации.*

Ключевые слова: *цифровая грамотность, коммуникация в социальных сетях, синтаксис и пунктуация, Telegram, неформальный язык, орфографические ошибки, языковые изменения.*

Introduction

If we define the concept of literacy, literacy is the ability of individuals to write, read, and express their thoughts clearly. In today's modern life, literacy encompasses not only reading and writing texts, but also the ability to correctly understand, interpret, and re-express information with one's own opinion. As UNESCO (2006) states: "Literacy is a key factor in personal and social development, providing individuals with the skills necessary for active participation in everyday life and society." [5] In addition, literacy plays an important role in linguistics, ensuring adherence to language norms, and the construction of logically, stylistically, and grammatically correct sentences. Nevertheless, several internal and external factors are causing a decline in literacy levels. In particular, the development of digital technologies and the widespread use of social networks are negatively affecting literacy. The habit of writing quickly and briefly on social media platforms is leading people to pay less attention to spelling and stylistic accuracy. According to Naomi Baron (2008): "The culture of fast writing and instant messaging prioritizes speed and convenience over grammatical and stylistic precision, leading to a decline in literacy levels." [1] This observation is highly relevant today. Furthermore, the decline in book reading is also contributing to the decrease in literacy. In the contemporary digital age, people tend to spend more time on social networks rather than engaging with books.

Methodology

In this study, real written communications were observed on Telegram and Instagram platforms. Text samples, including user messages, advertisements, and group posts, were analyzed to identify errors in spelling and stylistic structure. The main goal was to highlight how these mistakes impact literacy and the overall culture of written communication.

Results

The simplification and in formalization of language in communication have become major issues. The language used on the Internet and social networks is often simplified and does not meet grammatical and stylistic standards, which negatively affects not only written communication but also spoken language culture.

Today's digital age has changed the way people communicate with each other. Their conversations are faster, shorter, and often informal. Social networks such as Telegram, Instagram, and WhatsApp are now becoming the main means of communication. Currently, thousands of people express their opinions on such platforms. They use various personal opinions, advertisements, and group correspondence without paying attention to errors such as

spelling, lexical punctuation, etc. People usually prefer quick and short messages. However, as a result of these observations, it became clear that literacy, in addition to the impact of errors in correspondence, also has a negative impact on the quality of communication.

Currently, people make spelling mistakes in their messages due to haste, inattention, or low literacy during communication. For example, an advertisement for a course reads "A new group of English has been opened. "In such posts, the use of the letters and spelling is not given importance. In addition, in some texts, the inappropriate use of tense and person suffixes, and the writing of words based on their oral pronunciation are becoming popular, for example, the sentence in uzbek spoken language people often pronounce "bir nimalar" as "binnimalar", but in written texts it should correctly appear as "bir nimalar". The mistakes made as a result of such negligence not only negatively affect the literacy level of the writer but also give the impression to readers that they should write their thoughts faster and shorter in messages.

In the current age of technology, advertisements and announcements spread on social networks are usually used in the form of oral speech, in an informal language. For example, "You will speak English in 3 months," this message affects not only the official but also the credible appearance of the course. In fact, such messages in advertisements and announcements should be expressed in a sentence such as: "We will create an opportunity for you to speak English fluently in 3 months," which is a significant advantage in order and style. The correct and error-free use of words gains the attention and trust of the audience. We can see such mistakes around us every day, not only on social networks but also in advertisements hanging on the shelves of magazines and cafes. This negligence has a negative impact on language learners.

Discussion

The study revealed that the current trend of quick communication, informal style, and abbreviation on social networks significantly contributes to the deterioration of literacy standards. Errors in grammar, spelling, and stylistics not only reflect individual carelessness but also spread widely among users, gradually shaping a culture of writing that deviates from traditional norms. If left unchecked, this tendency can lower the general level of literacy, especially among young users who are most active on digital platforms. Comments on the Telegram and Instagram do show David Crystal's opinion about the Internet playing a serious role in the changes of the way of communication. As Crystal explains, people are chucking conventional punctuation and grammar aside in order to communicate more rapidly in a more efficient and more casual manner.[2] This change can be observed especially on Telegram or

Instagram, where it's all about direct communication and less about those details of the correct grammar. Emoji, acronyms, and partial sentences have become part of the fabric of quickly expressing what is on our minds now, sometimes replacing traditional punctuation or entire grammatical sentences. These shifts reflect a broader transformation the use of language in digital space. Moreover, the rapid exchange of messages on social platforms simplifies language structures, which significantly impacts syntactic consistency". This emphasizes how social media and digital platforms influence language, often causing speed and short messages.

Conclusion

In today's era of developing digital technology, the quality of each correspondence is of great importance. Each user should pay attention to spelling errors, punctuation marks, and follow the rules of style in their messages. Developing writing by paying attention to these errors can contribute not only to increasing the level of personal but also to the literacy of society and the development of a culture of communication. In the future, negligence and inattention to mistakes made because of preferring brevity and speed may lead to a decrease in the level of knowledge of young people. Therefore, it is necessary to introduce effective programs and control mechanisms to increase digital literacy.

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